

sponse was attributed to the inherently low level of these nutrients in the soil and to improved fertilizer N use efficiency resulting from their application.

The frequency of S or Zn application had no significant effect on rice yield. Rapeseed yields, however, were highest with 3 and 6 kg Zn ha⁻¹ every year. It was concluded that S and Zn should be applied to rice to obtain enhanced yields with an application frequency of 10 kg S ha⁻¹ in alternate years along with 3 or 6 kg Zn ha⁻¹ every year. This practice should prove advantageous over the years in realizing higher output from this important crop sequence in the Kashmir Valley. ■

Effect of S and Zn on yield in a rice-based cropping system in temperate Kashmir, India.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)					
	Summer crop (rice)				Winter crop (rapeseed)	
	1992 ^a	1993	1994	Mean ^b	1992-93 ^a	1993-94
Control (NPK only)	2.8	4.6	4.5	4.6	0.9	1.0
NPK + 10 kg S, E	4.0	6.2	4.8	5.5	1.0	1.4
NPK + 10 kg S, A	- ^c	6.1	5.0	5.6	-	1.3
NPK + 20 kg S, E	3.8	5.6	5.0	5.3	1.3	1.5
NPK + 20 kg S, A	-	5.9	5.1	5.5	-	1.3
NPK + 3 kg Zn, E	3.0	5.3	4.8	5.0	1.1	1.3
NPK + 3 kg Zn, A	-	5.6	4.8	5.2	-	1.1
NPK + 6 kg Zn, E	3.5	5.4	4.8	5.1	1.1	1.6
NPK + 6 kg Zn, A	-	5.6	4.9	5.3	-	1.3
NPK + 9 kg Zn, E	3.3	5.8	5.0	5.4	1.3	1.3
NPK + 9 kg Zn, A	-	5.2	5.1	5.1	-	1.1
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.3	0.7	0.2	-	0.1	0.2

^aSince this was the first year of experimentation, every (E) and alternate (A) years' values have been pooled and the means reported. ^bMeans of 1993 and 1994. ^c= no data.

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Effect of organic and inorganic fertilizers on sustainability of soil fertility and grain yield in a rice - wheat system

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We used inorganic fertilizers with organic amendments (farmyard manure [FYM], rice straw) and green manure

(GM) with dhaincha (*Sesbania aculeata*) to study yield, NPK uptake, and soil fertility.

The experiment began in 1985 at this station in the Jammu region. The soil is a clay loam Inceptisol with pH 7.1, EC 0.16 dS m⁻¹, 0.62% organic C, and 456.0 kg available N ha⁻¹, 13.80 kg P ha⁻¹, and 154 kg K ha⁻¹. Average N content (oven dry basis) was 0.71 % in FYM, 1.02% in dhaincha, and 0.36% in rice straw. The treatments were replicated four times in a randomized block design.

Rice variety Jaya was planted during the first week of July every year at 20- × 15-cm spacing. The 45-d-old GM crops were chopped and incorporated in the field 25 d before transplanting. The FYM and rice straw were mixed into the soil 15 d before transplanting. Plots were irrigated and 30-d-old rice seedlings transplanted in the puddled field. A wheat crop (variety HD2329) was sown during the third week of November every year at the rate of 100 kg seeds ha⁻¹ and chemically fertilized as required (Table 1).

Table 1. Grain yield (t ha⁻¹) as influenced by different treatments in rice - wheat cropping system. Jammu, India, 1985-93.

Treatment ^a	1985-87			1988-90			1991-93				
	Rice	Wheat	Total	Rice	Wheat	Total	Rice	Wheat	Total		
	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>									
T1	Control	Control	3.2	1.5	4.7	2.6	1.2	3.8	2.7	1.2	3.9
T2	50% F	50% F	3.6	2.4	6.0	3.7	2.5	6.1	3.5	2.4	5.9
T3	50% F	100% F	4.2	3.1	7.3	3.8	3.5	7.3	3.7	2.9	6.5
T4	75% F	75% F	4.5	2.8	7.3	4.0	3.0	7.0	4.0	2.6	6.6
T5	100% F ^b	100% F	4.9	3.2	8.1	4.4	3.6	8.0	4.6	3.1	7.7
T6	50% F + 50% FYM	100% F	4.4	3.4	7.8	4.2	3.8	8.0	4.9	3.3	8.1
T7	75% F + 25% FYM	75% F	4.8	2.8	7.5	4.4	3.2	7.6	4.7	2.9	7.6
T8	50% F + 50% rice straw	100% F	4.1	3.0	7.1	4.1	3.5	7.6	4.1	3.1	7.1
T9	75% F + 25% rice straw	75% F	4.7	2.9	7.5	4.4	3.3	7.7	4.3	2.8	7.1
T10	50% F + 50% GM	100% F	4.5	3.3	7.8	4.2	3.7	7.8	4.7	3.1	7.8
T11	75% F + 25% GM	75% F	4.7	3.0	7.7	4.4	3.3	7.6	4.7	2.9	7.6
T12	Conventional ^c	Conventional	3.6	2.0	5.6	3.1	1.8	4.9	3.5	1.8	5.3
CD (5%)			0.2	0.3	-	0.1	0.1	-	0.1	0.1	-

^aF = inorganic fertilizer; FYM = farmyard manure; GM = green manure (dhaincha). ^b100% F = rice (100 kg N, 26.4 kg P, and 24.9 kg K ha⁻¹); wheat (100 kg N, 22.0 kg P, and 20.7 kg K ha⁻¹). ^cConventional = farmer's practice of applying 60 kg DAP ha⁻¹ (basal) and 60 kg urea ha⁻¹ (topdressed).

At first, highest grain yield of rice and wheat during kharif was obtained with T5 (100% NPK through fertilizer). The treatments T7 (75% NPK + 25% N [FYM]), T9 (75% NPK + 25% N [straw]), and T11 (75% NPK + 25% N [GM]) gave higher rice yields than T6 (50% NPK + 50% N [FYM]), T8 (50% NPK + 50% N [straw]), and T10 (50% NPK + 50% N [GM]). During rabi, T6, T8, and T10 produced higher wheat yield than T7, T9, and T10, a result that may be attributed to 25% less NPK. The control recorded the lowest yield, and declined over the years. In later years, T6 and T10 have shown the highest response over the control, indicating that a 50% NPK saving could be achieved by continuous application of FYM or GM during kharif. Treatments T7 and T11 showed a 25% NPK saving. Total mean

productivity over the years in treatments T6 and T10 was comparable with that of T5.

Available N, P, and K (Table 2) decreased over the control after conventional treatment. Minimum depletion of N was observed in treatment T7 during kharif followed by T5 (100% NPK through chemical fertilizers in both seasons), T11, and T10.

Available P also decreased over the years, except for T5, where an appreciable buildup was observed. Available K content decreased in all treatments and maximum depletion was observed in the control.

These results suggest that combined use of organic and inorganic fertilizers can sustain soil fertility and grain yields in rice - wheat cropping systems. ■

Table 2. Effect of integrated nutrient supply on soil fertility changes under rice - wheat cropping system. Jammu, India, 1992-93.

Treatment no. ^a	Available nutrients (kg ha ⁻¹) after 8 yr					
	1992 kharif			1992-93 rabi		
	N	P	K	N	P	K
T1	179.2	5.42	87.0	162.0	5.10	82.5
T2	224.0	8.10	94.0	213.7	7.40	91.0
T3	251.0	8.80	94.5	247.5	8.25	91.0
T4	245.7	11.90	88.2	237.5	10.60	91.0
T5	310.2	20.40	101.4	301.0	17.90	97.4
T6	296.5	12.40	97.4	287.5	12.00	97.4
T7	327.0	16.80	102.0	310.5	15.25	97.4
T8	277.0	11.10	102.0	266.5	10.60	97.4
T9	278.0	11.10	98.5	271.1	10.85	98.5
T10	296.5	11.10	98.5	292.3	10.60	97.4
T11	301.0	10.90	87.2	292.3	10.60	83.5
T12	189.5	6.90	76.5	183.0	6.70	72.2
Initial	456.0	13.80	154.00			

^a See Table 1 for details.

Crop management

Effect of foliage pruning on performance of rice under semi-deep water situations (50-100 cm)

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We studied the response of rice yield to foliage pruning under excess water (>50 cm) at Cuttack during 1995 wet season using Panidhan (semi-tall, 180 d) and LPR312 (tall, 170 d) varieties. They were direct-sown in puddled soil the first week of June at 400 seeds m⁻¹ in 20-cm row spacings with basal fertilizers at 40 kg N ha⁻¹, 17.6 kg P ha⁻¹, and 33.2 kg K ha⁻¹. Foliage was pruned above the joint (collar) of the topmost leaf once or twice at 80, 100, and 120 d after germination (DAG). A split-plot design was used, data analyzed by standard analysis of variance, and treatment means were compared at the 5% level.

Crops emerged the second week of June, and by the first part of July, water level was 80 cm deep, fluctuating between 35 and 60 cm during crop growth period and receding gradually by crop maturity in mid-December.

Foliage pruning influenced plant growth (Table 1). Vertical growth picked up faster after first and second pruning but slowed down after third pruning. LPR312 produced more foliage than did Panidhan. Foliage taken at different times and frequencies differed from one another. Pruning at later growth stages gave more foliage than that at early stages. Interaction

between pruning and variety was not significant. However, LPR312 at delayed pruning gave more foliage than Panidhan. Foliage pruning was found detrimental to panicle growth and development, especially at later growth stages (Table 2). Panicle sterility was 2-3% higher with delayed pruning and two prunings compared with no pruning. Yield response also declined.

Table 1. Plant height and foliage yield of rice varieties at different times and number of leaf prunings.

Treatment	Plant height (cm)			Foliage yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	80 DAG ^a	100 DAG	120 DAG	Maturity	Fresh	Dry
<i>Variety</i>						
Panidhan	119	129	146	150	4.0	1.3
LPR312	116	133	157	164	4.9	1.6
CD (5%)	ns	ns	ns	ns	1.3	0.4
<i>Pruning</i>						
No pruning	116	137	166	174	-	-
One pruning at						
80 DAG	118	136	163	167	2.9	0.7
100 DAG	121	135	154	160	3.4	0.8
120 DAG	116	124	149	157	4.3	1.4
Two prunings at						
80 + 100 DAG	116	124	147	161	5.7	1.6
100 + 120 DAG	117	134	154	156	7.0	2.4
80 + 120 DAG	118	125	141	155	6.1	2.0
CD (5%)	ns	7.7	10.5	9.4	1.0	0.3

^aDAG - days after germination.